

Automatic quantitative metrical analysis of Spanish Poetry with Rantanplan: a first approach

Laura Hernández-Lorenzo
Digital Humanities Innovation Lab, UNED
laura.hernandez@scc.uned.es

Mirella De Sisto
Digital Humanities Innovation Lab, UNED
mdesisto@scc.uned.es

Álvaro Pérez
Digital Humanities Innovation Lab, UNED
alvaro.perez@scc.uned.es

Javier de la Rosa
Digital Humanities Innovation Lab, UNED
versae@gmail.com

Salvador Ros
Digital Humanities Innovation Lab, UNED
sros@scc.uned.es

Elena González-Blanco
School of Human Sciences and Technology, IE University
egonzalezblanco@faculty.ie.edu

Abstract

In this paper, we present a quantitative approach to Spanish poetry and versification through the application of our own automatic metrical tool, Rantanplan, to the complete poetic works of four Early Modern Spanish poets. The entire poetry by four representative authors of the period —Garcilaso de la Vega (1503-1536), Fernando de Herrera (1534-1597), Luis de Góngora (1561-1627), and Lope de Vega (1562-1635)—was automatically processed and stress positions were extracted. Thanks to the development of a new feature in Rantanplan for stanza identification, we could detect metrical structures as well. A quantitative analysis of stress positions, line lengths and stanzas used per author follows, aiming at modeling their complete metrical profile.

1 Introduction

The application of quantitative methodologies to poetry analysis has significantly grown in recent years, driven with the emergence of automatic tools for verse analysis. Although we count with reduced applications of these techniques to Spanish poetry, stress positions in sonnets and romances have already been assessed in a quantitative fashion. However, we are not aware of the existence of computational studies analyzing stanza information on the complete poetic works of an author.

In this article, we present a quantitative metrical analysis on a small corpus of Golden Age Spanish poets. Using our own automatic scansion and syllabification tool, Rantanplan (De la Rosa et al. 2020a) —which includes a new feature for stanza identification—a metrical annotation of the complete works by four canonical Spanish poets was performed. Due to the availability of their texts and their significance in this period, we selected Garcilaso de la Vega (1503-1536), Fernando de Herrera (1534-1597), Luis de Góngora (1561-1627), and Félix Lope de Vega (1562-1635). With the study and analysis of their metrical choices in terms of stress positions, line lengths and stanzas used, we aim at modeling their complete metrical authorial profile.

The paper is structured as follows: after this introduction, [section 2](#) contextualizes our research as part of the ongoing quantitative metrical approaches to poetry (with an especial focus on Spanish poetry). [section 3](#) introduces our study, the dataset used and how it was collected ([subsection 3.1](#)), as well as the methodology employed ([subsection 3.2](#)). [section 4](#) includes the quantitative metrical analysis, showing and discussing the results on stress positions ([subsection 4.1](#)), line lengths ([subsection 4.2](#)) and stanzas used by the authors ([subsection 4.3](#)). Finally, conclusions and future work are presented in [section 5](#). We include an Appendix with complementary materials.

2 Quantitative approaches to (Spanish) Poetry research

With the emergence of what we called nowadays Digital Humanities (Schreibman, Siemens, and Unsworth 2004), traditional Literature research has been enriched by the application of new methods and techniques. In this sense, quantitative approaches for the study of the literary record are notably growing, especially after the theories of distant reading by Moretti (2003); Moretti (2013) and macroanalysis by Jockers (2013). As Burrows declares, “computer-assisted textual analysis can be of value in many different sorts of literary inquiry, helping to resolve some questions, to carry others forward, and to open entirely new ones” (Burrows 2004).

In the case of Poetry, the application of quantitative methodologies and Natural Language Processing techniques has been less frequent than with narrative texts. At a first glance, this genre poses several limitations; some of the most important being the generally shorter length of poetic texts and their subjectivity. Despite of this, automatic analysis of poetic texts has received notable attention from the scholarly community in recent times. We count with academic studies applying these techniques, conferences and monographs dedicated to poetry studies in a quantitative fashion (Plecháč et al. 2019), and a growing number of tools especially developed for verse analysis. In this sense, we count with Natural Language Processing tools which perform automatic scansion and syllabification of poems. However, to the best of our knowledge, quantitative digital approaches using a combination of line and stanza information remain unexplored.

Regarding literary tradition, most quantitative and automatic verse studies have been applied to English poetry, with a reduced number of studies and tools available for other European languages. For the case of Spanish poetry, several automatic scansion and syllabification tools have been developed over the years since the first system built by Gervás (2000). Among these, Zeuscansion (Agirrezabal et al 2013), the ADSO Scansion system (Navarro-Colorado 2017) and Rantanplan (De la Rosa et al. 2020a) are the most recent ones. This rise of automatic tools has encouraged quan-

titative metrical studies of Spanish poetry, mainly carried out within the context of the ADSO¹ (Navarro-Colorado 2015; Navarro-Colorado 2016) and the POSTDATA² project (Ruiz Fabo et al. 2020), with the addition of a quantitative metrical project which does not use digital methods at the University of Neuchâtel: "Verse Rhythm in Golden Age Spanish Poetry: Lope de Vega and Luis de Góngora's Romances"³ (Sánchez Jiménez 2017; Llamas Martínez 2018).

In this sense, the ADSO project collected Golden Age Spanish sonnets from 52 different poets, which are automatically annotated with metrical information. From the analysis of these texts, Navarro-Colorado reaches conclusions about the preferred rhythmic patterns of each author when writing sonnets (Navarro-Colorado 2015; Navarro-Colorado 2016). At the studies conducted as part of the POSTDATA project, a bigger corpus of Spanish sonnets was collected, featuring poems from a wider range of dates —15th to 19th centuries—, and by more than 1000 authors. This allowed the researchers to analyze metrical patterns of sonnets after the Golden Age, with some interesting findings (Ruiz Fabo et al. 2020). Sánchez Jiménez (Sánchez Jiménez 2017) and Llamas (Llamas Martínez 2018) studied the corpus of Lope de Vega and Góngora romances to detect the metrical differences that arise between authors in this subgenre. In short, quantitative metrical research in Spanish poetry has mostly focused on sonnets and romances, neglecting the analysis of other subgenres as well as the analysis of the entire poetic production of an author.

3 Our study

This study aims contributes to the increased number of quantitative metrical studies presenting the metrical choices of four canonical Early modern Spanish poets. In doing so, we explore the complete metrical profile of each author, without restricting our analysis to a specific subgenre. This is possible thanks to the development of Rantanplan (De la Rosa et al. 2020a), which performs metrical analysis not only in hendecasyllables but in every type of Spanish verse. Moreover, its new feature of stanza and structure identification enables us to analyze the entire range of strophic and structure usage in every author.

3.1 Dataset

The first necessary step to carry out this project was to obtain the entire poetic works of Early Modern Spanish poets. In this sense, one of the limitations for quantitative approaches in Spanish Literature is the scarcity of available digitized texts in a suitable format, due to lack of digital editions and repositories. As a result, our choice was influenced by the relevance of the poet's works in Spanish Early Modern period

¹ADSO stands for "Análisis distante del soneto castellano de los Siglos de Oro" ("Distant reading approach to Golden Age Spanish Sonnets"). The project, led by Borja Navarro Colorado, was funded by a Fundación BBVA Digital Humanities grant. See more information about the project at its website: <http://adso.gplsi.es/index.php/en/adso-project/> [accessed: 19/11/2020].

²POSTDATA stands for "Poetry Standardization and Linked Open Data". The project, led by Elena González-Blanco, has received funding from the European Research Council. See more info at its website: <http://postdata.linhd.uned.es/> [accessed: 19/11/2020].

³This project was led by Antonio Sánchez Jiménez and funded by the Fonds National Suisse de la Recherche Scientifique. See more info at: <http://www.snf.ch/fr/encouragement/projets/projets-toutes-les-disciplines/Pages/default.aspx> [accessed: 19/11/2020].

as well as their availability. For this study, we used the complete poetry works of four Early Modern Spanish authors, namely, Garcilaso de la Vega (1503-1536), Fernando de Herrera (1534-1597), Luis de Góngora (1561-1627), and Lope de Vega (1562-1635). Garcilaso and Herrera are considered Renaissance poets, whereas Góngora and Lope are major representatives of Baroque style. Three of them have their entire poetic corpus available in the Web, while the fourth —Herrera’s corpus—is still to be published. For Garcilaso and Lope, we used the source texts provided respectively by Wikisource⁴ and Cervantes Virtual library⁵. For Góngora’s poetry we used the *gongocorpus*, a TEI-xml format corpus provided by Averell⁶, a tool developed within POSTDATA project (De la Rosa et al. 2020b).⁷ For the corpus of Herrera, we used the entire poetic works digitized in Hernández-Lorenzo (2020).⁸

In order to prepare our texts for the automatic metrical annotation —and to make sure there were not orthographic issues which could affect the analysis—we standardized orthography to contemporary Spanish, removed names of characters in dialogues, as well as rare symbols. We did not include in our analysis texts or fragments in languages other than Spanish.

Author	Poems	Words
Garcilaso	60	26.182
Herrera	91	18.685
Gongora	320	74.564
Lope	51	21.707

Table 1: Corpus of authors used, including number of poems and words of their complete poetry

3.2 Methodology

In order to metrically analyze our corpus of Early Modern Spanish poets, we rely on Digital Humanities quantitative methodologies, as described in section 2. We employ automatic scansion and syllabification by using the open-source Python package Rantanplan (De la Rosa et al. 2020a). Furthermore, we present an application of its new feature of stanza and structure identification, which works as follows: leveraging the information on metrical syllables and the stressed endings of each line of verse, our algorithm assigns rhyme per line with a customizable window. Both metrical lengths and rhyme patterns are then fed to a pattern matching algorithm using regular expressions that search for matches within a growing knowledge base of existing named

⁴Available at the following link: https://es.wikisource.org/wiki/Autor:Garcilaso_de_la_Vega [accessed: 20/11/2020].

⁵Available at <http://www.cervantesvirtual.com/obra-visor/poesias-liricas-0/html/ff775820-82b1-11df-acc7-002185ce6064.html> [accessed: 19/11/2020].

⁶Available at <https://github.com/linhd-postdata/averell> [accessed: 19/11/2020].

⁷The source texts for this last one are the digital editions of Góngora’s poems prepared in the prestigious POLEMOS project: <http://obvil.sorbonne-universite.site/corpus/gongora/> [accessed: 11/11/2020].

⁸The texts were digitized using the most complete and respected edition of his poems (Herrera 1975). As some of his works suffer from authorship problems and others present variants and different versions of the same text, we have limited our analysis to the poems and versions of the texts published in life of the author in *Algunas obras* (Herrera 1582).

structures and stanzas. The most complex match is then returned in both machine and human-readable formats, enabling scholars to pursue further investigations.

We annotated our plain text corpus in two different formats: firstly, containing only stress information; and, secondly, combining stress and stanza annotation. Then, we used a Python script for extracting and calculating the quantitative metrical data per author and compare them, considering stress position, verse length and type of stanza.

4 Quantitative metrical analysis

Quantitative metrical analysis allows us to gain a broad picture of a poet's metrical choices and to define which of them depend on the poetic school or on individual preferences. In this paper, we first compare the distribution of stresses in a line in the complete poetry corpora of Garcilaso, Herrera, Góngora, and Lope. By analyzing the recurrent stress patterns and the proportion of a specific stressed position in each corpus, we determine authorship features of the four poets. Subsequently, we take line lengths into account, in order to identify the use of different line lengths in the various authors; these characteristics also help identifying some authorship traits. Thirdly, we analyze the use of stanzas in the poetic works of the four authors. A quantitative analysis of the distribution of stanza types in the corpora contributes to define the authors' usage of different poetic forms.

4.1 Stress position

This section analyzes the proportion of stressed metrical positions in the four corpora. We refer to metrical positions, and not to syllables, because some phenomena can affect the one-to-one correspondence between the two elements. For instance, synaloepha, which is extremely widespread in Spanish poetry, can cause two syllables to count as one metrical position. Rantanplan (De la Rosa et al. 2020a) detects these phenomena and calculates the number of metrical positions accordingly.

On the one hand, the comparison between the distribution of stressed positions in the corpora highlights the poetic styles used by the authors and the literary school they belong to. On the other hand, this also reveals the poets' individual preferences regarding which metrical position to stress; these preferences are not strictly related to the style followed by the poet.

As shown in [Figure 1](#), based on stress patterns, the four authors can be split in two groups that represent the Renaissance and the Baroque styles: Garcilaso and Herrera show similar patterns, both being Renaissance representatives; Góngora and Lope constitute the Baroque group.

The most evident difference between the two groups is the amount of stressed syllables at the seventh and tenth positions. Góngora and Lope exhibit a strong common stress at the seventh position, while Garcilaso and Herrera tend to avoid it; the opposite situation occurs at the tenth position, which is strongly stressed in Garcilaso and Herrera's corpora and does not show a similar prominence in the works of the other two authors. The Renaissance group, besides the strong frequency of the stressed tenth position, also exhibit a recurrent stressed sixth position. The co-occurrence of stress at the sixth and tenth positions shows that Garcilaso and Herrera composed

Figure 1: Proportion of stressed metrical positions distributions in the line in the complete poetry by Garcilaso, Herrera, Góngora and Lope.

mostly hendecasyllables *a maiore*. The popularity of hendecasyllables in the two author’s corpora is evident also when only considering line-length, as it will be discussed in [subsection 4.3](#). The predominance of the *a maiore* pattern is in line with the findings of previous traditional and computational studies on Renaissance hendecasyllable ([Henríquez Ureña 1919](#); [Domínguez Caparrós 2014](#); [Navarro-Colorado 2015](#); [Navarro-Colorado 2016](#); [Ruiz Fabo et al. 2020](#)). In fact, the preference for patterns based on the scheme 6-10 (e.g. 2-4-6-10, 2-6-10) is significantly strong in Renaissance poets (for a detailed account, see [Navarro-Colorado \(2016\)](#)). This preference weakened in Baroque, where the most frequent pattern became 2-4-8-10 ([Navarro-Colorado 2016](#)).

By focusing on individual authors, stress pattern calculation also allows to identify poets’ distinctive features. Lope’s poetry stands out: he avoids stress at the second metrical position in favor of stress at the third one, while Góngora’s and the two Renaissance poets seem to prefer stress at the second position. The difference between Góngora and Lope can be explained by considering that, as observed by [Navarro-Colorado \(2016\)](#), stress on third position is a trait that gradually spread during Baroque until becoming particularly prominent at its later stages. Since Góngora is one of the first Baroque poets, this practice is not yet visible in his verse, while it is evident in a later poet like Lope.

A further aspect that distinguishes Lope from Góngora is that the former prefers a stressed sixth position while the latter exhibits more stressed seventh positions.

Finally, even though Garcilaso and Herrera’s metrical patterns turn out to be quite similar, some distinctive traits appear: in Garcilaso, a second, sixth and ninth stressed positions are slightly more frequent than in Herrera; in Herrera, instead, third, fourth and eighth positions tend to be stressed more often than in Garcilaso.

4.2 Line length

Measuring line-lengths distributions allows us to identify which poetic forms are more represented in each of the corpora. Line length is calculated by considering the number of metrical positions per line. As shown in [Figure 2](#), two groups can be defined based on the line-length distribution, namely Renaissance and Baroque poets.

The strongest difference between the two groups is attested at the tenth metrical position. In the Renaissance group, the great majority of lines has ten metrical positions, which indicates that these authors mostly wrote hendecasyllables. However,

Figure 2: Proportion of line-lengths distributions, based on number of metrical positions, in the poetry by Garcilaso, Herrera, Góngora, and Lope

the Baroque authors do not show preference for one line length and have more varied line sizes in their poetry; the most common line length in their poetic works is seven metrical positions. Finally, Lope’s poetry is the most varying in terms of line length.

4.3 Stanzas used

Quantitative results of stanza detection were obtained by using Rantanplan (De la Rosa et al. 2020a) and calculating the percentages of each type of stanza for each author, and the total number of identified stanzas per author (see the table repository mentioned in the Appendix). Out of 47 stanza types, 20 are not used by the four Early Modern Spanish poets.⁹ Some of them are typical of the Medieval period, such as the *estrofa manriqueña*, *copla de arte mayor*, *copla de arte menor*, *copla real*, *copla mixta*, *décima antigua* or the *cuaderna vía*. Another undetected type, the haiku, has not been employed in Spanish poetry until recently.¹⁰

The rest of the stanzas are used by at least one author, with only five being used by all of them: sonnets, couplets, *octavas*, *serventesios* and *tercetos*. Garcilaso and Herrera write *liras*, whereas Góngora and Lope favour *sextetos liras* —especially Lope, with 17,05% of his detected stanzas. The two Baroque poets also employ some popular stanzas, such as *seguidillas*, *septillas* or *romances*, which are not detected in the Renaissance poets. The most used stanza in three of the authors is the *terceto*, whereas more than 50% of detected stanzas in Góngora are *cantares*, also known as *coplas*. Another stanza quite typical of the period, the *octava real*, is heavily used by Garcilaso and Góngora, but not by Herrera and Lope. These results are related to our previous observations regarding stress positions and line lengths. In this sense, the popular stanzas that emerge in the baroque poets, as well as the *cantares*, are not

⁹The non-detected stanzas are the following: *copla de arte mayor*, *copla de arte menor*, *copla real*, *cuaderna vía*, *décima antigua*, *endecha real*, *estrofa manriqueña*, *estrofa sáfica*, *haiku*, *octava mixta*, *octavilla*, *ovillejo*, *quinteto*, *seguidilla compuesta*, *seguidilla gitana*, *septeto lira*, *sexteto*, *silva arromanzada*, *soleá* and *terceto monorrímo*.

¹⁰Among the rest of the not detected stanzas and structures, it is interesting that the four poets do not write some hendecasyllabic stanzas and structures, such as the *estrofa sáfica*, the *terceto monorrímo*, the *quinteto*, the *sexteto*, the *septeto lira*, the *endecha real* or the *silva arromanzada*. Regarding popular stanzas and structures, the *octavilla*, the *ovillejo*, the *seguidilla compuesta*, the *seguidilla gitana* and the *soleá* are not used.

hendecasyllabic and confirm the smaller amount of this type of verse in Góngora and Lope.

Among the most used stanzas, sonnets and *tercetos* are of particular interest due to their big proportion in many of our authors. For this reason, we analyze more closely the usage of these two stanzas.

The comparison of sonnets relative frequencies in the four poets is shown in Figure 3. Lope favors this stanza type, which constitutes over 17% of his detected stanzas. Herrera follows him with a percentage of use of nearly 15%. In contrast, Garcilaso and especially Góngora employ sonnets to a lesser extent, with a percentage of use below 10%.

Figure 3: Percentages of sonnet's writing. Lope is the author who uses more sonnets (over 17% of his detected stanzas), followed by Herrera (almost 15%). Garcilaso and Góngora employ this structure to a less extent (below 10%).

As aforementioned, the *terceto* is the stanza that achieves a higher percentage of use in three of the four poets. However, it greatly varies among them. On the one hand, for both Garcilaso and Herrera, nearly 70% of the detected stanzas are *tercetos*, with over 78% of Herrera's poetic production identified as such. On the other hand, this stanza is much less frequent in the two baroque poets. In this sense, *tercetos* are well below 50% in Lope and do not even represent 3% of Góngora's detected stanzas.

Figure 4: Percentages of *terceto*'s writing. Herrera is the one who favors this stanza (over 78% of his detected stanzas), followed by Garcilaso (almost 70%). *Terceto*'s percentage of use decreases in Lope (around 35%) and even more in Góngora (less than 3% of his detected stanzas).

5 Conclusions and future work

This paper has applied quantitative methodology to metrical analysis in Spanish Poetry, focusing on four representative authors of the Early Modern period, through the application of an automatic scansion and syllabification tool, Rantanplan. Thanks to the development of a new functionality for stanza identification in this software, a complete analysis of the metrical choices of the selected authors was performed. With the aim of modeling their metrical authorial profile, we based our analysis on the quantitative data of stress positions, line lengths, and stanzas. Our results confirm previous hypothesis and provide new insights.

The predominance of *a maiore* patterns and the preference of patterns based on the scheme 6-10 is in line with the findings of previously traditional and computational research on Renaissance hendecasyllable. Also, even when differences in stress positions delimitate two different group of poets, the Renaissance and the Baroque ones, there are enough distinctive features to identify each of the authors.

Regarding line length, our results show that the two Renaissance authors mostly write hendecasyllables, whereas the Baroque ones exhibit a wide variety of types of verses. This is more evident in our quantitative stanza analysis, since shorter-verse, popular stanzas emerge in the Baroque poets, with a striking abundance of *cantares* in Góngora. Likewise, close examination of the most used stanza, *tercetos*, clearly suggests that this generally hendecasyllabic stanza is far less frequent in the Baroque than in the Renaissance authors.

However, all these findings are restricted to a small number of authors. Thus, for future work, we would like to expand the corpus of poets in this period with the goal of corroborating the data obtained in this study for Renaissance and Baroque authors.

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Appendix

A complete table which contains the relative values on percentages of the results of stanza and structure detection in the four corpora can be found in a repository available at https://github.com/linhd-postdata/Plotting_Poetry2020. This reposi-

tory also contains the corpora that have been used in this project, except for Herrera's texts, which have not been published yet; however, Herrera's corpus annotations are included in the repository.